

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ «ACTION RESEARCH» В ПРЕПОДАВАНИИ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Новые требования рыночных отношений, предъявляемые к современному специалисту, требуют динамичных изменений в системе образования нашей страны. Обновление содержания образования - это ответный шаг на современные реалии. Новая система образования ставит перед преподавателями новые задачи - совершенствование педагогического мастерства преподавателей в контексте обновления образовательной программы, введение системы критериально-ориентированного оценивания, а по сути, повышение функциональной грамотности выпускников.

ABSTRACT

New requirements of market relations to the modern specialist, requires a dynamic change in the education system of our country. Updating the content of education is a reciprocal step to modern realities. The new education system sets new goals for teachers - improving the pedagogical skills of teachers in the context of updating the educational program, introducing a system of criteria-based assessment, and, in fact, improving the functional literacy of graduates.

Ключевые слова: методология, Action Research, исследование в действии, развитие учителей.

Keywords: methodology, Action Research, research into action, teacher development.

Simple literacy is no longer sufficient for the citizens of the Republic of Kazakhstan. They must be prepared to continually learn the most advanced work skills involving new equipment and state-of-the-art productions. This necessity extends to general education schools, where there is a need for education that ensures the formation of an intellectually and spiritually developed personality. Such education is critical for the success and social adaptation of citizens in a rapidly changing world. To achieve these goals, a modern teacher must enhance their professional competence to improve the quality of education. Action Research serves as one of the means for self-education and self-development of teachers.

The terms "contextual research," "action research," or "active research" are used when translated into Kazakh. Robin McTaggard (1989) defined "action research in education" as the study of the outcomes of the pedagogical process conducted by teachers in schools to enhance its effectiveness[1,121].

"Action research" is identified as a systematic research process that enables individuals to find effective solutions to real problems encountered in daily life.

Historically, the concept of "action research" has been closely linked to the work of German social psychologist Kurt Lewin, who pioneered the idea. Lewin observed that experimental methods often fell short in many scenarios. He sought a method rooted in the real-life experiences of individuals[2,256].

According to Kurt Lewin, "action research" is a comparative study of the conditions and consequences of various forms of social action and research that leads to social action. Thomas Gilmore succinctly stated that "action research" aims to investigate the practical problems faced by individuals in direct problem situations, while simultaneously contributing to the objectives of social science. This dual commitment necessitates active collaboration between the researcher and the client, underscoring the significance of collaborative learning in the research process[4,160].

O'Brien described "action research" as a natural blend of acting and researching simultaneously[5,153]. Dick echoed this sentiment, emphasizing that "action research" lives up to its name by aiming to achieve both action and research concurrently. This approach is vital for teachers seeking to implement changes in learning

while being conscious of those changes[6,37].

Hutchinson and Lomax highlighted that "action research" focuses on studying curriculum issues and, particularly, the management of school and institutional change[7,85]. Carr and Kemmis emphasized the research goals of "action research," defining it as a form of reflexive research undertaken to enhance the rationality and fairness of one's own practices, understanding the practices and the conditions under which they occur[8,203].

Burns recognizes that action research is an important tool for studying the school and the classroom. He states that the objectives of educational research are usually divided into categories that reflect action research:

- a means of eliminating problems in certain situations or improving a certain set of conditions.
- tools for teachers to learn new skills and methods, expand their analytical skills and increase their self-awareness.
- a means of introducing complementary or innovative approaches to learning into an established system that usually discourages innovation and change.
- a tool to improve communication between practicing educators and academic researchers and to overcome the failure of traditional research to provide concrete recommendations.
- a means of providing a suitable alternative to the more subjective, impressionistic approach to classroom problem solving [9, 160].

According to Glickman, " Action research " is research that teachers conduct to solve problems in their classrooms [10, 24]. In addition, Calhoun research work

Traditionally, educational research has involved making beneficial changes to teacher or student learning. As teacher-researchers, they want to conduct research in their classrooms or schools to improve instruction, implement and evaluate newly developed educational theory or educational plans.

According to Hopkins, the selection of teachers for professional development is based on the following criteria:

- The teacher's primary role is teaching and research, which should not interfere with or detract from this commitment;
- The method of data collection should not be too demanding on the teacher's time;
- Teachers must be able to confidently formulate hypotheses and classroom situations that are sufficiently reliable to allow the development of applicable strategies;
- The teacher must be faithful to the research problem being studied;
- The teacher must follow ethical procedures for conducting research;
- Form and share a common vision in the classroom whenever possible; perspective should be taken into account [12, 167].

"Action research" has some features. Many scholars have tried to describe research activity in terms of school research. McDonough suggests the following four characteristics of research activities:

1. Is aimed at the participants and clearly shows them;
2. Cooperation;
3. Leads to changes and improvements in practice, not only in knowledge itself;
4. Depends on the context. Research activities are conducted in the classroom by a specific teacher or group of teachers who work together to change or improve teaching and learning problems [13, 75-78].

And Creswell suggests six main characteristics of research activity:

1. practical orientation;
2. teacher-researcher's own experience;
3. cooperation;
4. dynamic process;
5. action plan;
6. division of studies [14, 102].

Creswell states that understanding the above characteristics can assist teachers in better planning their research to read, evaluate, and utilize practice studies published in the literature. This is then delineated into seven steps as follows:

Step 1: In this phase, the problem is identified, evaluated, or formulated, or a general understanding of the question that the participant wants to change or improve is provided.

Step 2: At this stage, it is necessary to discover the facts to gain a complete picture of the situation, assisting the researcher in determining the nature of the problem.

Step 3: This step involves critical consideration of the problem identified in the second step. It aims to review the research literature to identify what can be learned from comparative studies, including their aims, procedures, and the challenges they encounter. Typically, at this stage, the researcher formulates hypotheses that attempt to clarify aspects of the problem.

Step 4: Here, the researcher starts to collect relevant information to test the hypotheses presented in the previous stage. However, it is important to note that testing hypotheses does not involve statistical testing, but rather an effort to show the consistency of actual data with the hypotheses. Levine also suggests that even after testing a hypothesis, it should remain a "hypothesis" rather than a "conclusion," as there may be scenarios where the hypotheses are not applicable.

Step 5: During this phase, the teachers and other members of the collaborative group discuss research procedures, including the selection of materials, teaching methods, assignment of tasks, and so on. They deliberate and make decisions.

Step 6: This stage sees the participants engage in the implementation of the action plan. They establish the conditions and methods for data collection, classification, and analysis, they also jointly monitor the completion of tasks and deliberate on the selection of assessment procedures.

Step 7: This includes the interpretation of collected data and the overall assessment of the study. At this stage, the research cycle might be repeated. At the end of each cycle, the findings are reviewed, suggestions and trials are proposed, and so forth. It is anticipated that the outcomes will eventually be brought to

public attention [14, 142-149].

Considering "action research" as research, Noonan develops seven stages of the "action research" cycle:

Step 1: Initiation-problem generates an action research idea

Step 2: Preliminary investigation - initial data is collected to help understand the nature of the problem.

Step 3: Hypotheses- Hypothesis is formulated after considering the original

Step 4: intervention - a series of strategies are developed and used.

Step 5: Evaluation - An evaluation is conducted to evaluate the intervention.

Some steps may be repeated.

Step 6: Dissemination-study report published. We share ideas that emerge from our research.

Step 7: Alternative solutions to the subsequent service-problem are constantly being explored [15, 237].

To simplify, Gay and Erazian suggest the following basic steps in action research:

Step 1: Identify a topic or question for research;

Step 2: collect data related to the selected topic or issue;

Step 3: analysis and interpretation of collected data;

Step 4: Carry out action planning, which is the application of action research findings [16, 304].

In contrast, Creswell describes the action research procedure as a detailed 8-step process:

Step 1: Determine if action research is the best design;

Step 2: define the research problem;

Step 3: Find resources to help you solve the problem;

Step 4: Determine the required information;

Step 5: Perform data collection;

Step 6: Analyze the data;

Step 7: Create an action plan;

Step 8: Implement and reflect on the plan [14, 163]

In short, the action research processes described above differ in that they are basic, simple, or complex models. In the course of research, one can find models that are more or less suitable than others, depending on specific situations and learning situations.

Directions of scientific research in the field of education Problems related to education arise in school. Thus, the problem of action research in education is related only to the following areas:

1. Teaching Practice: This field refers to actual teaching in the classroom. Related to learning technology, i.e. method, textbooks, homework and other resources.

2. Behavioral issues: the ultimate goal of education is to achieve the necessary changes in the behavior of students. Sometimes some students start behaving out of the ordinary. Matters related to this aspect belong to this field.

3. Co-curricular activities: Co-curricular activities are an integral part of the curriculum. The problem is that they are not used properly at school.

4. Administration and organization: Creating a healthy school environment is a special need today.

Therefore, it is very important to solve the problems related to this area.

5. Assessment: Assessment is an important part of the learning process. A sound and reliable assessment is an urgent need.

There are some advantages of applied research in education.

For teachers, practical research can have a number of advantages. They include thinking about educational practice, identifying strategies for improvement, and developing research skills. Collaborative action research has the added benefit of engaging teachers and school principals to work together to improve educational outcomes.

"Action research" research is aimed at solving an actual problem in a certain educational environment, namely: teacher researchers study a practical problem that can benefit education. In addition, researcher-teachers engage in practical research primarily based on their own situation rather than someone else's experience. In this context, they engage in "collaborative" or "self-reflective learning," in which they reflect on what they have learned and what they can do to improve their educational situation.

As researchers, teachers and students as recipients of change benefit greatly from action research. Considered the educational aspect of action research.

Teachers explore their practice in new ways, exploring what they and their students really do and don't do.

Teachers develop a deeper understanding of the process of student learning and their role in educating both teachers and students.

Teachers are seen as equal partners in making decisions about what needs improvement in their classrooms. In most cases, the solutions to the identified problems are jointly accepted by the teachers.

Teachers are often more inclined to practice research because they identify areas that they see as problematic and in need of change. Action research is a continuous process and its strategies can be widely used. School professional development and improvement are key aspects for any teacher engaged in practical research.

Teacher reflection can be done individually or in a school group consisting of students, teachers, and administrators.

Borgia and Schuller recognized the importance of action research in education and stated that action research:

- encourage change in schools;
- encourages a democratic approach to education;
- expands the opportunities of individuals thanks to cooperation in projects;
- positions teachers and other educators as learners who attempt to bridge the gap between their practice and their vision of education;
- encourages teachers to reflect on their own experiences;
- contributes to the process of testing new ideas [17, 286].

Action research has several limitations. In theory,

it can be both descriptive and experimental. Most studies utilize descriptive designs yet attempt to draw conclusions about the impact of actions on outcomes. Rarely do action research studies employ experimental methods, like control groups or random assignment, which lend strength to experimental research. Therefore, inferences about causality are credible only when based on robust experimental designs.

Another limitation is that most studies are confined to a single classroom or school, preventing the generalization of results to other settings. Consequently, empirical research often lacks the internal and external validity necessary for informed policy decision-making.

Researchers engaged in "action research" operate amidst the complexities of their experiences. Meticulous observation of practices within this context demands both space and time, and maintaining rigor in data collection and analysis is challenging.

Action research is conducted by individuals who are involved parties, leading to critiques of research validity and claims of bias in data collection and analysis.

Ignorance of research methods by some researchers can also be problematic.

Researchers often must learn about adequate research methods while investigating their own experiences. Such impromptu training and planning can result in unreliable data collection, although reliable data gathering is critical.

Researchers in "action research" emphasize the concept of commitment. An action researcher must scrutinize and evaluate their practice diligently, a task complicated by the difficulty in measuring commitment.

Results from action research are often not generalizable. However, the insights and conclusions drawn can be tested by others in different contexts.

Finally, depictions of the "action research" process can be perplexing. Various diagrams outlining this process differ in complexity and might not always aid understanding. They can foster a misleading sense of uniformity in teachers. Action research is a fluid process, loosely connected to the main trajectory of research, various lines of inquiry, and continuous realignment. Hopkins (1993) criticizes inflexible, prescriptive models as potentially constraining teachers to a structure they might rely on excessively, thereby curtailing independent initiative. The terminology of "action research" can also be perplexing or contradictory to the process's fundamental principles.

The idea of creating the Action Research approach belongs to Lewin, a psychologist who founded the dynamic theory of personality. The framework of Action Research includes action (solving real problems in real situations) and research (trying to achieve the goal of scientific recognition). The idea of the AR approach is not to discover something unknown for psychological-pedagogical theory, but to develop critical thinking skills, with the help of which it is possible to independently correct existing ideas about various aspects of pedagogical activity or, on the contrary, check their correctness and clarify their action plan. The main prin-

ciple approach is that the researcher can identify the difficulties or problems observed during his professional activity only within his personal experience. The research should be conducted directly by the practitioner himself or by a group of practitioners who independently identify the problem in their professional activities.

Action research is a spiral process that includes three points: planning, taking action, gathering facts about the results of action. For convenience, these stages are divided into the following stages:

- Stage 1 - Diagnostic. Identify the problem or problem the teacher wants to explore.
- Stage 2 - Estimated. Collect reference information based on the analysis of relevant literature and existing research on this topic. Development of a system of measures aimed at solving the problem.
- Stage 3 - Practical. Research and plan data collection methods.
- Stage 4 - Generalization. Data collection. Conclusion. Data analysis and interpretation
- Stage 5 - Introduction. Record, share and implement research findings.

School-based action research is a process that enables practitioners to analyze, think about, and solve school problems.

This form of research is actually not only about acquiring knowledge, but also about how to contribute to it. Based on this, the main goal of the teacher is to participate in the process of self-reflective research in order to understand and improve his practice.

Pedagogical research participants focus their action efforts on curriculum change, challenging existing school practices, and seeking social change through a continuous process of problem-posing, data collection, analysis, and action.

Teachers are often taken aback by problems that arise in the classroom and actively seek solutions. The moment a teacher implements changes, they begin action research, systematically gathering evidence on the impact of these changes.

Action research can empower teachers to think systematically about their practice. The underlying premise is that teachers are innately equipped to handle the challenges associated with the teaching profession.

The key to success in teaching is ongoing growth and learning. Action research is an effective method for teachers to continue evolving and learning through hands-on experience. It starts from the teacher's current state and refines practice as needed.

The purpose of my research was to ascertain the relationship between enhancing functional literacy in the department and the use of active teaching methods.

Based on the lessons conducted, it is concluded that the potential to develop functional literacy is not dependent on teaching methods alone. However, not all students can engage in developing functional literacy through passive methods. Utilizing active or interactive methods aids in elevating the functional literacy of all students by boosting each individual's cognitive activity.

Inherently, action research is a cyclical process. Insights from the outcomes of prior research can lead

to new problems, giving the research an ongoing nature. By adopting the role of a "pedagogical leader and researcher in action," the teacher remains engaged in evaluating and seeking enhancements for teaching and learning practices.

During my research, it was discovered that students had a limited understanding of research and design activities. Thus, completing the first cycle of research identified a new objective for the subsequent cycle.

Indeed, the ongoing identification of new tasks, problems, or solutions underscores the cyclical nature of this approach.

In summary, teachers can utilize action research as a tool for enhancing foreign language teaching, refining and acknowledging their professional experience, and fostering self-development and professional growth.

The concept of modernizing the modern Kazakhstani school has established new priorities for general education, indicating that the learning process model should be based on diverse teaching methods. These methods enable various educational activities and foster cooperative relationships between teacher and student.

A modern *teacher* can focus on such topical issues as improving the understanding and use of modern innovative pedagogical technologies, the updated educational content program, formative and criterion-referenced practices, and assessment, increasing enthusiasm for learning, interdisciplinary integration, using various non-standard teaching methods and strategies, working with gifted children. work At the same time, static data

validation tools allow you to share your experience with colleagues based on valid and validated results.

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